

COLLOCATIONAL CHOICES IN THE DISCOURSE ACTIVITIES OF SELECT PARAMILITARY AGENCIES

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Abstract

This paper investigated the collocational choices used among three Nigerian paramilitary formations in their official discourse activities with a view to ascertaining the contextual meanings of the lexical combinations. Data for the study comprised of 114 collocated items collected by means of participant observation and key informant interview (KII) of randomly selected segments of the personnel while in office environments, patrol duties and muster parades. The findings showed that personnel of the formations used peculiar collocational choices in their formal discourse engagements which revealed a high level of competence that enhanced in-group mutual intelligibility and solidarity among members. Categorically, the collocational choices occurred in eight different combinations: noun-noun, adjective-noun, verb-noun, adverb-adjective, adverb-verb, adverb-noun, noun-adjective and verb-adverb made up of lexically compatible items to advance institutionally modelled meanings. The lexical collocations are prominently two content words in the open class system that showed linguistic appropriateness and stylistic felicities. They are formulated to communicate professional orientation to facilitate the discharge of the security and safety-related statutory duties of the agencies.

Keywords: Collocational choices, Lexical collocations, Discourse activities, Paramilitary Agencies, Paramilitary language, Nigeria

Résumé

Cet article étudie les choix de collocation utilisés dans les discours officiels en trois formations paramilitaires au Nigeria en vue de déterminer les significations contextuelles des combinaisons lexicales. Les données de l'étude comprennent 114 éléments collectés par le moyen d'observations participantes et d'entretiens avec des informateurs clés (EIC) de sections sélectionnés au hasard du personnel dans les environnements officiels, des tâches de patrouille et des parades de

rassemblement. Les résultats montre que le personnel des formations utilise des choix de collocation particuliers quand il s'engage en de discours formels qui révèle un niveau élevé de compétence qui améliore l'intelligibilité mutuelle au sein du groupe et la solidarité entre les membres. Catégoriquement, les choix de collocation se produisent dans huit combinaisons différentes : nom-nom, adjectif-nom, verbe-nom, adverbe-adjectif, adverbe-verbe, adverbe-nom, nom-adjectif et verbe-adverbe composé d'éléments lexicalement compatibles pour avancer des significations institutionnellement modélisées. Les collocations lexicales sont en général deux mots dans le système de classe ouverte qui montrent la pertinence linguistique et la beauté stylistique. Ils sont formulés pour communiquer une orientation professionnelle afin d'assurer l'accomplissement des obligations statutaires des agences en matière de sécurité et de sûreté.

Mots clés : Choix de collocation, Collocations lexicales, Activités discursives, Agences paramilitaires, Langage paramilitaire, Nigeria

Introduction

The increasing proliferation of occupational groups appears to have occasioned the creation of peculiar lexical forms for use in order to attend to the emerging communicative needs of different professions. This situation stimulates the creation of sub-types of the variety of English for occupational purposes which is advanced to provide distinctions in terms of function and purpose of certain registers. As it is the practice in work-related domains of language use, "every language has developed means for the differentiation of distinct function and association. And our knowledge of language (involves the ability to) recognize, interpret and originate all the subtle functions in relation to varying needs of our personal, social, political and professional involvements" (Moody, 1970, p. 2). Therefore, for social inclusion in professional discourse activities, it is expected of the participant(s) to develop the obligatory communicative competencies in order to recognise, generate and interpret the peculiar variety associated with the professions they belong to. One such example is the variety used in the paramilitary formations in Nigeria. The paramilitary agencies, which have been in existence in Nigeria for decades, operate on different legal bases but primarily perform aspects of safety and security-related responsibilities depending on the specifications in their different Establishment Acts. From the period of their legal creations, the members had, and are still using English as the medium to facilitate the discharge of their official duties. The essential duties include: the maintenance of law and order, safety of lives and property, ensuring the safety of travellers on the highways, minimizing the rate of traffic crashes, protection of government's critical infrastructure, and defending the civilian population. The dissimilarity in terms of their administrative structures and functions tend to have a considerable influence on their language. This would particularly establish

linguistic pointers that differentiate them from other institutions of government which should prompt investigation.

The study is anchored on the premise that there exists inadequate or no knowledge on the vast communicative activities of the three agencies, and particularly on the collocational choices prevalent in their interactive activities, in spite of their decades of existence. Perhaps, the nature of the institutional roles of the agencies may have informed the idiosyncrasy in their official communicative events that establish social inclusion and out-group bias. The apparently confined knowledge of such elements is bound to create communication barrier during their interactions with non-members. The study is therefore designed to examine the collocational choices used in the language of the Nigerian paramilitary formations, particularly: the Nigeria Police Force (NPF), the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) and the Nigeria Security and Civil Defense Corps (NSCDC) using Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria as the case study. These are federal government agencies with Commands spread across all the states in Nigeria. Basically, the NPF checks all criminalities, the FRSC concentrates on road traffic matters while the NSCDC secures government's critical assets. As agencies of the government, it is presumed that the clarifications on the institutional (contextual) usage of the lexical combinations by the personnel in the target State should bear linguistic correlation with those of the selectional patterns used by their counterparts in other parts of Nigeria.

Literature review

Collocation, as aspect of proficiency in communicative activities, has been defined by many scholars. It is said that "collocations of a given word are statements of habitual or customary places of that word" (Firth, 1968, p. 133). It is also viewed as "a group of words that occurs repeatedly, that is, reoccurs, in a language" (Benson, 1985, p. 61). Collocation can also occur where "a word goes together, relates or naturally selects the other word to help define its meaning in a sentence" (Shitu, 2015, p. 327). The co-occurrence of words is often determined by the intended meaning. That is, "collocation is highly determined by meaning, it is sometimes idiosyncratic and cannot be easily predicted in terms of the meaning of the associated words" (Nofal, 2012, p. 77). The habitual co-occurrence and association of particular words determine the referential and contextual meaning. In terms of its classification, collocation is subdivided into: grammatical, lexical and restricted collocations (Robins, 1964; Benson, 1985; Bahns, 1993; Fontenelle, 1998; Lewis, 2000; Nofal, 2012). Grammatical collocation contains a content word followed by a functional one which is often a preposition, infinitive or participle (advised by, commit to, among others). The lexical category has two open class or content words of equal lexical elements in

terms of function, without any subordinating functional word (good man, talking drum) while restricted collocation is structurally patterned with selectional restriction in words combination (commissioned officer, pump action).

This study is concerned with the aspect of collocational choices and the selectional restriction. Distinguishing collocational restriction from the others, Matthews (2007, p. 63) states that it is “any restriction on the collocability of one individual word with another”. In another study, it is viewed as “the restrictions on how words can be used together” (Richards & Schmidt, 2012, p. 87). It is also used to address “the possibility of occurrence of largely two or more words in lexical relations” (Demir, 2017, p. 76). From the above explications, they imply that collocational restrictions are often syntactic in form with selectional limitations in terms of choice of lexical components that are semantically compatible in the domain and context of use. The structural pattern which determines the non-idiomatic or technical meaning of the expression is usually drawn from the particular registers and delimited by the field of discourse. These features enable the identification of collocated elements from different discourse domains.

In Nigeria, Taiwo (2004), Okoro (2013) and Shitu (2015) have carried out studies on collocations. Their investigations are either focused on collocations as a stylistic practice in English usage in Nigeria or learning aspects of speakers of English as a second language. According to the studies, the collocational patterns are evidence of transfers and interference from the mother tongue which may have some variants from the target standard. This set of studies are concerned with collocations as they occur in general English usage and not as aspects of English for occupational purpose that reveal the job-related contexts.

What appears as studies on collocations in the English usage of the paramilitary in Nigeria are in the investigations by Ebong (2009) and Udo (2010). Rather than adopting them as collocations, Ebong and Udo classify them as linguistic features in their separate studies on the NPF. They aver that such creative choices enhance the secluded formal communication practice of the NPF. One of the studies on language use in Nigerian paramilitary formations, states that the forms are created to conceal feminine identity in the male dominated paramilitary forces (Uwen & Ekpe, 2018a). Another opinion on this discourse is Uwen and Ekpe’s (2018b) investigation on language and national development which uses the Nigerian security organisations as a case study. The authors in this particular research, conclude that the devised forms which portray communicative competence, are meant to facilitate the effective discharge of duties of the personnel. A separate study on the competence and content analysis of the English language of the

Nigerian paramilitary operatives corroborates the claim that such terminologies are institutional expressions. There are outcomes of the developed competence by the security agents which highlight the peculiarity of their style of language use (Uwen & Ukam, 2019). In a different view, Uwen (2019) explains that such constructs are components of the morphological features in the English language of the Nigerian paramilitary formations. From the reviewed opinions above, it is believed that the lexical choices and their use by the personnel represent institutional formulations that index in-group comprehension arising from the competencies required to ease the execution of the sensitive duties they perform. The focus of the reviewed studies is not particularly targeted at the explanations of the in-group mutually intelligible collocational restrictions. This study is therefore aimed investigating the collocational choices and their peculiar use in the speech events among the NPF, FRSC and NSCDC. The study would strive to provide the semantic evaluation of the collocated forms in the context of language use in the agencies.

Theoretical framework

The linguistic model adopted for this study is Collocational competence. It is a subset of communicative competence which accounts for the competence in the knowledge, application and use of collocational expressions to measure proficiency of participants in specific discourse practices. Collocational competence is a native speaker's linguistic phenomenon used to distinguish competencies of native speaker and second language learners (Bazzaz & Samad, 2012; Mahyelati & Mukundan, 2012). The authors believe that collocational competence is central to, and an important factor in the measurement of speakers' knowledge on the combinations of compatible and incompatible words in different discourse domains. This is achievable through the exposure to, and consistent use of all the linguistic levels of the target language by its speakers. Other studies are certain that the attainment of the described stage of competence is the hallmark of a linguistically advanced speaker of a language because it is where proficiency is attained. (Zhang, 1993; Taiwo, 2004; Demir, 2017). In fact, Demir (2017, p. 77) specifically stresses that "there is nearly no way of using language without referring to collocations because they are intricately interwoven with the language itself". The possible inappropriate patterns, according to scholars, often occur as a result of inadequate collocational knowledge and learning strategies, especially by second language learners (Taiwo, 2004; Anari, & Ghaffarof, 2013; Davoudi & Bahshad, 2015; Shitu, 2015). The knowledge of the sequence and frequency of habitually co-occurring lexical and functional words in a language is believed to be developed simultaneously and consciously along the learning stages of any language through which such errors can be corrected. As proficiency improves, the occurrence of this category of errors

becomes minimal and eventually phased out. Collocational competence as a linguistic phenomenon is relevant to this study because, aside from being a pertinent aspect of the broader notion of communicative competence, it is appropriate and contained in the competencies attained in the use of English for occupational purpose. In this consideration, only the members of the group that choose to, and belong to a specific profession are obligatorily expected to attain the competence. The attainment suggests the expression of the speaking skills in the usage of occupational variety of English where collocational competence for in-group interactions is embedded. Since collocations in English are transnational, the errors (that is, if there are) will be ‘minimal’ among the native speakers of English, when compared to the research population who are L2 users of the language. The use of collocational choices in terms of the frequency and proficiency by the operatives of the agencies under study points towards the personnel’s competencies in the institutional language which underscores the relevance to the study.

Methodology

The data for this study were obtained by means of participant observation of unsolicited official speech events of some segments of the operatives in the office, parade grounds and routine patrol duties using the random sampling technique. Participant observation is a qualitative research technique where an investigator who is also a member of a social group observes and participate in its activities to generate data. Also, key informant interview (KII) is a technique used to elicit information from spoke persons of social groups or organisations who are believed to be knowledgeable in the activities of the group. This is applied on the Public Relation Officers (PROs) of the target security organisations: NPF, FRSC and NSCDC in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The mentioned organisations are among the disciplined services in Nigeria which have restricted access to their “formal” discourse activities. The collection of data is aided by the fact that the researcher has worked in one of the services for over a decade, and as an insider, he has permissible access to their interactive sites. He does this as an active participant, participant observer and even in the informal engagement of the spoke persons of other similar agencies in order to extract the collocations in the interactions. From the notes derived from the communicative activities of the respondents, 114 institutionally-driven collocations of different co-occurring content words were extracted from the corpus which form the data for the analysis.

Results and discussions

The data comprise unique collocational restrictions which are integral components of the group’s institutional expressions. The paradigms in this

category are presented in the order of their combinational occurrences as follows: noun-noun, adjective-noun, verb-noun, adverb-adjective, adverb-verb, adverb-noun, noun-adjective and verb-adverb respectively. Each of the sets of combinations consists of two co-occurring open class words with accompanying institutional/contextual meaning.

Collocational choices and the meanings

In the context of the discourse domains of the selected Nigerian paramilitary formations, the distinctiveness of the collocating forms shows the scope of restrictions in the choice of words that portray the orientation, ideology and official schedules of the operatives. The meanings are expressed in the context of the institutions as presented below.

Noun - noun combination

The first category of content words combination is the noun-noun order. Nouns are by their nature stative, often referring to or assigning names to entities that are either abstract or tangible in form. In this class of collocations, the preceding noun performs the function of the modifier and/or qualifier to the succeeding noun by giving a descriptive information about it as contained in the examples below.

Noun + noun	Collocates	Contextual meaning
Assault + rifle	assault rifle	a sophisticated gun authorized to be used by security personnel
Rifle + range	rifle range	the distance a rifle's bullet can travel especially during combat trainings
Gun + powder	gun powder	Harmful substance used in guns
Bail + bond	bail bond	signatory to the bail conditions of a criminal suspect
Bribe + taker	bribe taker	a member of the agencies that is corrupt
Gang + leader	gang leader	leader of a criminal group being trailed by security agents
Unit commander +	unit commander	a senior officer in charge of a section of the uniformed forces
Intelligence report +	intelligence report	an investigated secret information that aids in the curbing of criminality
Situation report +	situation report	report on official assignment meant to guide further action
Danger + zone	danger zone	a dangerous area or criminal hide out
Patrol + leader	patrol leader	the head of a security patrol team
Patrol + rank	patrol rank	ranks range permissible for patrol

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		operations
Traffic + offence	traffic offence	traffic violation
Parade + commander	parade commander	an officer who commands a regimental parade
Muster + parade	muster parade	a parade mounted for a commanding officer to review
Parade + state	parade state	report on the numerical strength and physical conditions of officers and men on parade
Offence + ticket	offence ticket	a ticket stating traffic violations(s)
Private + detective	private detective	a secret informant used in criminal investigations
Sentry + post	sentry post	a small shelter at the entrance of paramilitary commands mounted by the rank and file
Guard + room	guard room	a room where erring personnel are detained as punishment or to ease investigations on them
Road + rage	road rage	aggressive driving on the road meant to cause harm to others
Exhibit + room	exhibit room	a room where confiscated items are kept for further investigation or presentation in the court
Statement + form	statement form	a form used to record the statements of defaulters/suspects' involvement in criminal matters
Intelligence + officer	intelligence officer	the head of the intelligence unit that operates covertly
Personnel + profile	personnel profile	secret but vital information on personnel's lifestyle
Crime + scene	crime scene	the exact spot where a crime was committed
Accident + scene	accident scene	the spot where accident occurred
Sting + operation	sting operation	a planned exercise to detect a high profile crime
Road + audit	road audit	an investigation on roads' situation for recommendations to the government
Head + dress	head dress	official cap for uniformed services
Car + snatcher	car snatcher	criminal who steals cars especially at gun point
Enemy + camp	enemy camp	area where unfriendly forces reside to carry

		out criminal activities
Oil + thief	oil thief	a criminal who steals petroleum products
Skid + mark	skid mark	The mark on the road created by the sudden application of car brake before accident occurred
Death + trap	death trap	a very bad and accident-prone road or portions of the road
Enemy + forces	enemy forces	unfriendly criminal elements who thwart the efforts to check criminalities
Eye + service	eye service	working pretentiously to impress superiors which is usually practiced by subordinates
Body + bag	body bag	bags used to wrap dead accident victims
Colour + party	colour party	a special parade regiment in national events
Guest + room	guest room	a cell
Sister + agency	sister agency	other security agencies other the agency one belongs to
Speed + hump	speed hump	elevations built or mounted on the road to check speed
Rader + gun	radar gun	a device for tracking speed
Riot + shield	riot shield	a protective equipment used by security forces to prevent harm from angry mob/crowd
Police + station	police station	police office higher than the police post
Jungle + justice	jungle justice	unlawful punishment (killing) by angry civilians
Fire + arms	fire arms	authorised ammunitions used by security personnel

Adjective - noun combination

The second set of collocational choices used among the Nigerian paramilitary formations has the co-occurrence of adjectives and nouns. Adjectives modify or qualify nouns by giving useful information about the nouns. Stylistically, they function structurally as nouns which are concrete or non-concrete entities. In the context of this study, the nouns are sufficiently described by the information supplied by the preceding adjectives which help in giving the institutional meaning of the combinations as seen below.

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Adjective + noun	Collocates	Contextual meaning
Peak + cap	peak cap	ceremonial cap used by members of uniformed services in specific occasions
Stray + bullet	stray bullet	where a fired bullet targeted at a criminal hits an unintended target
Wanted + criminal	wanted criminal	a criminal declared wanted by government authorities
Investigating officer	investigating officer	an officer authorised to investigate crime
Private + security	private security	Licensed security outfits other than government's
Ceremonial parade	ceremonial parade	parades for paramilitary and government ceremonies
Adulterated product	adulterated product	petroleum product confirmed to have been contaminated
Critical infrastructure	critical infrastructure	a very important government facility
Fatal + crash	fatal crash	a road accident that claims one or more lives
Principal + suspect	principal suspect	the major suspect in a criminal activity
Special + patrol	special patrol	a patrol organised to detect a particular crime or offence
Confessional statement	confessional statement	self-admittance to crime in writing
Criminal + record	criminal record	a person with a criminal account of commission of crimes
Electronic + ticket	electronic ticket	electronically generated traffic offence ticket
Summary + trial	summary trial	a quick trial of a defaulting personnel to award punishment
Major + entry	major entry	a punishment arising from the trial of a personnel
Criminal + gang	criminal gang	a criminal group
Recalcitrant driver	recalcitrant driver	continuous violation of traffic rules by a driver
Armed + robber	armed robber	a thief who carry out his nefarious activities with arms

National + assets	national asset	a facility owned by the government
Blind + spot	blind spot	an area of the road not seen by the driver while driving
Black + spot	black spot	accident-prone area of the road
Commissioned + officer	commissioned officer	a personnel superior to the rank and file
Superior + officer	superior officer	a senior officer
Inflammable + liquid	inflammable liquid	all petroleum products
Bloody + civilian	bloody civilian	a term used to describe non-members of the security agencies
Accidental + discharge	accidental discharge	sudden discharge of a bullet
Tinted + permit	tinted permit	a written authority to use tinted glass
Tinted + glass	tinted glass	non-transparent car glass
Reprobate + offender	reprobate offender	a serial traffic violator
Drunk + driver	drunk driver	a driver driving under the influence of alcohol
Reasonable + force	reasonable force	a minimum force applied to effect arrest
Forceful + entry	forceful entry	unauthorised entry into a secured place
Malicious + damage	malicious damage	spiteful damage to property
Friendly + forces	friendly forces	law abiding groups and citizens
Mobile + court	mobile court	special court for trial of traffic violators
Regimental + game	regimental game	competition among security agencies
High + command	high command	authorising superior office
Force + headquarters	force headquarters	national headquarters

Verb - noun combination

The next combination is the verb-noun. The verb is the action or doing word. Verbs do this by denoting the events and processes. Verbs are traditionally referred to as action words. Verbs are the message carriers because, at the structural level, they provide the link with and to other elements. When combined with nouns as it is in the examples below, they describe the action undertaken by

or message concerning the nouns as practiced in the interactive segments of the research population.

Verb + noun	Collocates	Contextual meaning
Advance + mine	advance mine	come towards my direction
Shoot + target	shoot target	a superior directive to shoot on the intended object
Shooting + range	shooting range	an area for practicing bullet range during trainings
Arresting + marshal	arresting marshal	the junior cadre who accost erring drivers to be booked
Booking + sheet	booking sheet	a traffic offence ticket
Commanding + officer	commanding officer	the head of a paramilitary agency at the state level
Reviewing + officer	reviewing officer	the commanding officer who inspects parade
Search + warrant	search warrant	a written authorisation to search a suspect's residence
Reinforcing + failure	re-enforcing failure	providing back up for a failed battle/operation
Crossing + sword	crossing sword	a practice in ceremonial wedding for officers
Flash + point	flash point	a troubled spot/area where criminal activities are prevalent
Guard + duty	guard duty	security duties performed by the rank and file
Check + point	check point	a spot for stop and search of vehicles along the road to detect crimes
Tear + gas	tear gas	a powdered substance for dispersing crowd
Flying + ticket	flying ticket	a ticket issued to a booked vehicle owned by a known person/institution
Flying + vehicle	flying vehicle	a vehicle plying a dangerous speed
Foisted + crime	foisted crime	forceful abortion of intended crime

Adverb - adjective combination

There is also the category where adverb co-occurs with the adjective. Adverbs traditionally modify the verbs, adjectives and (in some instances) the adverbs in the clauses. In terms of functions, they 'move' with the verbs and also provide more information about them. They are the most flexible word class in terms of

its dangling positioning at the sentential level. They can occupy the initial, medial or final position in sentences depending on the writer or speaker. In the context of the paramilitary discourse, they modify the succeeding adjectives by conveying information on how or what nature is the adjective is. The collocational choices in this category are in the examples below.

Adverb + adjective	Collocates	Contextual meaning
Criminally minded	criminally minded	a person with records of criminality and predictive criminal intention
Mechanically deficient	mechanically deficient	a rickety vehicle that is potentially dangerous to ply the roads

Adverb - verb combination

Again, there is another set where the adverb takes the verb. Adverbs also modify verbs (see 5.1.4). In this manner, they perform the modification function on the action or event by describing ‘how’ the action was carried out through a derivation process from the adjectives by adding the *-ly* suffix. In the paramilitary English usage, they modify the action words in the collocations below.

Adverb + verb	Collocates	Contextual meaning
Reasonably + suspected	reasonably suspected	a criminal suspected with a glaring evidence
Readily + admit	readily admit	admitting willingly to the commission of a crime
Roughly + handled	roughly handled	maltreatment of a civilian or personnel

Adverb - noun combination

Although traditionally, adverbs modify adjectives, verbs and adverbs, but there are circumstances where they also modify the nouns as the case in paramilitary interactions where the adverbs describe the nature or degree of the nouns they collocate with. The collocational choices used among the personnel that fall in this category are shown below.

Adverb + noun	Collocates	Contextual meaning
Counter + attack	counter attack	an attack in response to that of an opponent
Over + socialization	over socialisation	amorous relationship between a senior and junior personnel

Noun - adjective combination

The noun-adjective form is also observed in speech events of the target respondents. In the example below, the noun assumes the role of an adjective through the modification of the preceding adjective by describing its state or degree.

Noun + adjective	Collocates	Contextual meaning
Red + alert	red alert	ready for action

Verb - adverb combination

The final collocating words found to be used among the group under investigation is the verb-verb order. In this selectional pattern, the verb takes the adverb. The verbs in combination with the adverbs as shown in the examples below, perform the traditional role of denoting action and describe the extent by which the actions are to be carried out.

Verb + adverb	Collocates	Contextual meaning
Investigate + thoroughly	investigate thoroughly	a more equipped in depth finding to bring reliable information on a criminal activity
Act + swiftly	act swiftly	proactive action by security personnel in threatening circumstances
Supervised + lazily	supervised lazily	a senior personnel who monitors official assignments absent-mindedly

Figure 1: Bar chart showing the frequency and percentage distribution of the variables

From Figure 1 above, the distribution of the variables in terms of the frequency of their occurrence shows that there are 47 collocational choices in the noun-noun combination from the total 114 items, adjective-noun occurs 39 times, verb-noun appears 17 in the corpora, adjective-verb takes three, verb-verb has 3 three, adverb-adjective two, adjective-noun two while the least is the noun-adjective category which has one item. The percentage distribution (approximated) in the order above is 42, 34, 17, three, three, two, two and one respectively. The implication of the revelation is that the formal interactions among security organisations in Nigeria have the ‘largest’ corpora of collocational elements from the noun-noun group followed by those of the adjective-noun, verb-noun, adjective-verb and verb-verb, adverb-adjective and adjective-noun, and noun-adjective which has the least. The co-occurring words are derived from their formal interactions during investigations, security activities, human and vehicular traffic control, arrests and prosecutions of offenders and criminal elements. Noun is the dominating element in terms of frequency count, this is in order because, so it is in the collocational in any standard corpus of English.

The nature of the collocational elements and their institutional usage

The selectional pattern of the collocating elements involve the choice of words from the open class system: the nouns, adverbs, verbs and adjectives, with the absolute exclusion of the close system elements such as the prepositions, conjunctions and interjections (Lewis, 2000; Nofal, 2012). There is also the exclusion of the specific and non-specific modifiers: *the*, *a* and *an*, and other demonstratives: *that*, *this*, *those* and *these* as the study has shown. The lexical collocational choices in the present study corroborates Bahns (1993) and Fontenelle's (1998) position that the category of collocations explained in this study restrictively combines nouns, verbs, adverbs and adjectives and do not accept subordinating elements such as infinitives and prepositions. The open class elements are "combined easily with each other in the structure of a given utterance" (Eka, 1994, p. 30). As it is the case in the restrictions above, the content elements can undergo various forms of inflectional changes depending on the co-habiting elements. Such modifications often account for the different conditions they represent: plurality, nature of reference, time and possession (Eka, 1994). For instance, the nouns in the examples in this study, represent things, places, persons or abstractions which are modified by the adjectives. The adjectives also describe the quality, state or action while the adverbs like in other contexts, perform modification and qualification roles informing us of the nature of the actions as well as the semantic clues of the verbs. The verbs used in the examples above, represent the grammatical category markers that stress the mood, tense, aspect, person and number, and in some other instances refer to the state or action that is in progress.

It is also observed the members of the research population have a high level of mutual intelligibility of the choices, except for a few that may be exclusively related to any of the formations. On institutional basis, co-habitual words such as bail bond, police constable, guest room, force headquarters, tear gas, readily admit, police station, among others are peculiarly used by the NPF. Also, collocational choices like electronic ticket, booking sheet, arresting marshal, road audit, reprobate offender, major entry, blind spot, radar gun and flying ticket are often found in interactions among the FRSC. In the NSCDC, there is the frequent use of collocations such as: critical infrastructure, private security, oil bunkering, national assets, adulterated product and exhibit yard, among others. There are also other collocational restrictions that express the collective professional orientation, ideology and job schedules of the group in this study. The entries in this category are the sentry post, parade state, eye service, head gear, ceremonial parade, bloody civilian, summary trial, commanding officer, regimental game, guard room and crossing sword combine to express their orientation. In the same vein, sister agency, reasonable force, enemy forces, criminally minded, over

socialization, red alert, reprobate offender, flash point, personnel profile and road rage communicate the ideology of the agencies. The collocations that characterise the official schedules of the formations include: patrol leader, traffic offender, arresting marshal, shoot target, riot shield, accident scene, investigating officer and search warrant.

Conclusion

The study has revealed the selectional patterns of the collocational choices contained in the language of the Nigerian paramilitary formations with clarifications their 'isolated' meanings. As shown in the study, the choices are selected from the English open class elements which are lexical and content words collocating in compatible relationships for meaning orientation. The expressions which convey situated meanings, were created to facilitate the execution of the crucial safety and security-related responsibilities of the NPF, FRSC and NSCDC. The collocational choices, except for a few (bribe taker, oil thief, death trap, guest room, among others) which bear semantic extensions in the Nigerian English usage, others appeared to have transnational mutual intelligibility among work groups that perform similar duties. The study, aside from creating the materials on new horizons for investigation, it has created awareness and broaden knowledge on in-group language of the paramilitary. This sensitization, it is believed, would bridge the communication gap between members and non-members especially during interactions where such collocations are used. The study recommends further research on language use in the military and paramilitary agencies in order to broaden the knowledge and competence that would attend to the needs-based communication when involved in formal conversation exchanges with the target personnel.

References

- Anari, S. M. & Ghaffarof, S. (2013). The effect of collocational competence on translation accuracy of translation trainees. *Journal of Advances in English Language Teaching*, 1(3), 76-84.
- Bahns, J. (1993). Lexical collocations: A contrastive view. *ELT Journal*, 17(1), 56-63.
- Bazzaz, E. F. & Samad, A. A. (2011). The use of verb-noun collocations in writing stories among Iranian EFL learners. *English language Teachings*, 4(3), 158-163.
- Benson, M. (1985). Collocations and idioms. In R. Ilson (Ed.), *Dictionaries, lexicography and language learning*. Oxford: Pergamon Press.
- Davoudi, M. & Behshad, A. (2015). Collocational use: A contrastive analysis of strategies used by Iranian EFL learners. *Theory and Practices in Language Studies*, 5(12), 2646-2652.
- Demir, C. (2017). Collocations in English: A comparative study of native and non-native scholars of English. *Journal of Language and Linguistics*, 13(1), 75-87.
- Ebong, S. E. (2009). *A stylistic study of the language of the Nigerian Police*. Unpublished Masters' thesis, University of Uyo, Nigeria.
- Eka, D. (1994). *Elements of grammar and mechanics of the English language*. Uyo: Samuf Limited.
- Firth, J. R. (1968). A synopsis of linguistic theory. In F. R. Palmer (Ed.), *Selected papers of F. R. Firth 1952-1959*. Bloomington & London: Indiana University Press.
- Fontenelle, T. (1998). Lexical functions in dictionary entries. In A. P. Cowie, *Phraseology: Theory analysis and applications*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Lewis, M. (Ed.) (2000). *Teaching collocations: Further developments in lexical approaches*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Malvelati, E. H. & Makundan, J. (2012). The role of cognitive style in the collocational knowledge development of Iranian EFL Learners through input food treatment. *English Language Teaching*, 5(10), 105-117.
- Matthews, P. H. (2007). *Oxford concise dictionary of linguistics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Moody, H. L. (1970). *Varieties of English*. London: Longman

- Nofal, K. H. (2012). Collocations in English and Arabic: A comparative study. *Journal of English Language and Literature Studies*, 2(3): 75-93.
- Okoro, O. (2013). Exploring collocations in Nigerian English usage. *California Linguistics Notes*, 37(1), 85-121.
- Richards, J. C. & Schmidt, R. (2012). *Longman dictionary of language teaching and applied linguistics* (3rd ed). Edinburgh: Pearson Education Ltd.
- Robins, R. H. (1964). *General linguistics: An introductory survey*. London: Longman.
- Shitu, F. M. (2015). Collocation errors in English as a second language (ESL) essay writing. *International Journal of Cognitive and Language Sciences*, 9(9), 3270-3277.
- Taiwo, R. (2004). Helping ESL learners to minimize collocation errors. Retrieved on July 2, 2019 from [http:// iteslj.org/Techniques/ Taiwo-collocation.html](http://iteslj.org/Techniques/Taiwo-collocation.html).
- Udo, V. (2010). The linguistic features of the Nigerian Police Force, Onitsha. Unpublished Master's thesis, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Uwen, G. O. (2019). Morphological features in the English language of selected Nigerian paramilitary formations in Akwa Ibom State. *English Linguistic Research*, 8(1), 48-54.
- Uwen, G. O. & Ekpe, S. I. (2018a). De-echoing feminine identity in the language of three Nigerian Paramilitary agencies. *Abuja Journal of Gender Studies and Youth Advancement*, 1(1-2), 55-74.
- Uwen, G. O. & Ekpe, S. I. (2018b). Language and national development: The case of Nigerian security organizations. *Calabar Journal of Liberal Studies*, 20(2), 328-336.
- Uwen, G. O. & Ukam, E. I. (2019). A competence and content analysis of the English language of select Nigerian paramilitary operatives. *Currents in African Literature and the English Language*, 10: 123-132.
- Zhang, X. (1993). *English collocations and their effect on the writing of native and non-native college freshmen*. Indiana: University of Pennsylvania Press.